

Acclimatization and Ionic Antagonism with Sheep Serum and other Colloids.

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W. Spring [*Bull. Acad. Roy. Belg.*, [3], 38, 483 (1900)] and H. Freundlich [*Zeit. physikal Chem.*, 44, 143 (1903)] and H. B. Weiser [*J. Phys. Chem.*, 23, 309 (1921)] stated that the amount of electrolyte necessary for coagulation of a sol is greater when the addition of the electrolyte to the sol is slow and spread out for several days than when it is rapid and the coagulation is finished quickly. We [*J. Phys. Chem.*, 29, 659 (1925); 31, 649 (1927); *Kolloid-Z.*, 37, 141 (1926)] have made a systematic investigation of this phenomenon of acclimatisation and have observed this phenomenon with sols of arsenious sulphide, antimony sulphide, mastic, gum dammar, Prussian blue, gold, ferric hydroxide, and positively charged manganese dioxide, when coagulated by electrolytes which yield similarly charged ions capable of being adsorbed by the sols.

We have also observed that in the coagulation of arsenious sulphide and antimony sulphide by strychnine hydrochloride, quinine hydrochloride, crystal violet and methylene blue, and negatively charged manganese dioxide by silver nitrate and cupric sulphate, smaller quantities of electrolytes are necessary when the addition is slow and spread out for a long time than when the coagulation is rapidly finished. We have termed this phenomenon as negative acclimatisation. We have shown that cause of positive and negative acclimatisation lies on the ratio of adsorption of positive and negative ions by the sol. When a sol does not adsorb similarly charged ions and an ion carrying the opposite charge is highly adsorbed, we always get the phenomenon of negative acclimatisation.

We [*J. Phys. Chem.*, 30, 830 (1926) *Kolloid-Z.*, 29, 346 (1926)] have shown that that sols like arsenious sulphide, antimony sulphide, Prussian blue, cupric ferrocyanide, gum dammar, mastic and gamboge are appreciably hydrolysed and the stability of these sols depends upon the degree of hydrolysis. Hydrogen ions markedly retard this hydrolysis and make the sols unstable.

We have also shown that the phenomenon of ionic antagonism observable with certain sols is more pronounced when the sols are diluted and also depends on the ratio of adsorption of two ions.

In this paper, we have investigated the influence of dilution on the phenomenon of acclimatisation with sols of arsenious sulphide, mastic and gum dammar. We have also studied the coagulation of sheep serum by a mixture of electrolytes and by the slow addition of acids and salts.

TABLE I.

Acclimatization of a concentrated arsenious sulphide sol.

Concentration of the sol = 3.29 gms. As_2S_3 per litre. Amount of sol taken each time = 2 c.c. Volume = 6 c.c.

Time of observation = 1 hr. after adding the last quantity of the electrolyte.

Electrolyte.	Amount to coagulate when the electrolyte is added all at once.	Quantity added at a time for slow addition.	Amount to coagulate when added slowly.	% Difference.
NaCl N/2	1.2 c.c.	0.2 c.c.	1.30 c.c.	+8.3
CH_3COONa N/2	2.1	0.3	2.50	+19.0
HCl N/4	1.6	0.3	1.40	-12.5
HNO_3 N/4	1.6	0.3	1.40	-12.5
H_2SO_4 N/4	1.65	0.3	1.50	-9.1
CH_3COOH N	2.9	0.4	2.70	-6.9

TABLE II.

Acclimatization of a dilute arsenious sulphide sol.

Amount of sol taken each time = 0.5 c.c. Time of observation = 1 hr. after the last quantity of the electrolyte is added. Volume = 6 c.c.

Electrolyte.	Amount to coagulate when added all at once.	Quantity added at a time for slow addition.	Amount to coagulate when the addition is slow.	% Difference.
NaCl N/2	1.35 c.c.	0.2 c.c.	1.45 c.c.	+7.4
CH_3COONa N/2	2.50	0.3	3.00	+20.0
HCl N/4	1.60	0.3	1.30	-18.7
HNO_3 N/4	1.60	0.3	1.35	-15.6
H_2SO_4 N/4	1.65	0.3	1.40	-15.2
CH_3COOH 4N	3.00	0.4	2.65	-11.6

TABLE III.

Acclimatization of a concentrated mastic sol.

Concentration of the sol=4.23 gms. mastic per litre. Amount of sol taken each time=2 c.c. Time of observation=1 hr. after the last addition of the electrolyte. Volume=6 c.c.

Electrolyte.	Amount to coagulate when added all at once.	Quantity added at a time for slow addition.	Amount to coagulate when the addition is slow.	% Difference.
NaCl N	0.65 c.c.	0.1 c.c.	0.70 c.c.	+8.3
CH ₃ COONa N	1.85	0.3	2.05	+10.8
HCl N/100	1.20	0.2	1.10	-8.3
HNO ₃ N/100	1.20	0.2	1.10	-8.3
H ₂ SO ₄ N/100	1.25	0.2	1.15	-8.0

TABLE IV.

Acclimatization of a dilute mastic sol.

Amount of sol taken each time=1 c.c. Time of observation =1 hr. after the last addition of the electrolyte. Volume=6 c.c.

Electrolyte.	Amount to coagulate when added all at once.	Quantity added at a time for slow addition.	Amount to coagulate when the addition is slow.	% Difference.
NaCl N	1.05 c.c.	0.1 c.c.	1.15 c.c.	+9.5
CH ₃ COONa N	2.90	0.3	3.30	+13.9
HCl N/100	1.20	0.2	1.05	-12.5
HNO ₃ N/100	1.20	0.2	1.05	-12.5
H ₂ SO ₄ N/100	1.25	0.2	1.05	-16

TABLE V.

Acclimatization of a concentrated gum dammar sol.

Concentration of the sol=4.28 gms. gum dammar per litre.

Amount of sol taken each time=2 c. c. Time of observation =1 hr. after the last addition of the electrolyte. Volume=6 c.c.

Electrolyte.	Amount to coagulate when added all at once.	Quantity added at a time for slow addition.	Amount to coagulate when added slowly.	% Difference.
NaCl N	0.8 c.c.	0.1 c.c.	0.9 c.c.	+12.5
CH ₃ COONa N	1.8	0.3	2.05	+13.9
HCl N/100	1.10	0.2	1.00	-9.0
HNO ₃ N/100	1.10	0.2	1.00	-9.0
H ₂ SO ₄ N/100	1.20	0.2	1.10	-8.3

TABLE VI.

Acclimatization of a dilute gum dammar sol.

1 c.c. of the sol is taken each time. Volume=6 c.c. Time of observation=1 hour after the last addition of the electrolyte.

Electrolyte.		Amount to coagulate when the addition is all at once.	Quantity added at a time for slow addition.	Amount to coagulate when added slowly.	% Difference.
NaCl	N	1.5 c.c.	0.2 c.c.	1.65 c.c.	+10.0
CH ₃ COONa	N	2.95	0.4	3.4	+15.3
HCl	N/100	1.10	0.2	0.9	-18.2
HNO ₃	N/100	1.10	0.2	0.9	-18.2
H ₂ SO ₄	N/100	1.20	0.2	1.05	-12.5

The foregoing tables show that the phenomenon of negative acclimatization is observed with sols of mastic, gamboge and arsenious sulphide when coagulated by acids and the phenomenon is more pronounced in the dilute sols.

In the following tables we shall record our results on the coagulation of sheep serum by different salts and acids. 6 C.c. of serum when heated in a water-bath for 90° minutes left a residue of 3.38 gms. The viscosity of the serum at 30°=0.01345, whilst that of water at 30°=0.00803. 2 C.c. of original serum taken.

Total volume=10 c.c.

Time of observation=1 hour.

TABLE VII.

Coagulation by Salts.

Salts.	Amount required to coagulate in c.c.	Coagulating concentration.
Sodium acetate 3.4M	7.80	2.6520
Sodium tartrate 1.32M	6.90	1.8216
Potassium oxalate 1.5M	6.45	1.8350
Potassium fluoride 8.0N	1.90	1.5200
Cerous nitrate N/200	5.35	0.00267
Aluminium nitrate N/200	5.20	0.00260
Thorium nitrate N/200	5.60	0.00280

Hence the coagulating powers of different salts are in the following decreasing order:—

Al(NO₃)₃ > Ce(NO₃)₃ > Th(NO₃)₄ > K₂F₂ > sodium tartrate > K₂C₂O₄ > sodium acetate.

TABLE VIII.

Coagulation by Acids.

Acids.		Amount required to coagulate in c.c.	Coagulating concentration.
Nitric	N/200	6.8	0.0084
Hydrochloric	N/200	7.0	0.0085
Sulphuric	N/200	7.2	0.0086
Phosphoric	N/50	4.7	0.0094
Formic	N/50	1.85	0.0037
Acetic	N/50	1.90	0.0038
Monochloroacetic	N/50	1.80	0.0036
Dichloroacetic	N/50	2.0	0.0040
Trichloroacetic	N/50	2.0	0.0040
Oxalic	N/100	3.2	0.0082
Tartaric	N/100	4.0	0.0040
Citric	N/100	2.8	0.0028

Hence the coagulating powers of different acids are in the following decreasing order :—

Citric > oxalic > nitric > hydrochloric > sulphuric > monochloroacetic > formic > acetic > dichloroacetic > trichloroacetic > tartaric > phosphoric.

The influence of dilution towards the coagulation of the serum has also been investigated and the following results were obtained :—

Serum A=2 c. c. of original serum.

Total volume=10 c. c.

Time of observation=1 hour.

TABLE IX.

Electrolytes.	A/2 Serum.	A Serum.	3A/2 Serum.
Sodium acetate 3.4M	9.0 c. c.	7.8 c.c.	6.6 c.c.
Sodium tartrate 1.32M	7.5	6.9	6.65
Potassium fluoride 8N	2.15	1.9	1.8
Potassium oxalate 1.5M	6.8	6.45	6.0

TABLE X.

		A/5 Serum.	A Serum.
Cerous nitrate	N/200	1.65 c.c.	3.85 c.c.
Aluminium nitrate	N/200	1.5	5.2
Thorium nitrate	N/200	1.7	5.6

TABLE XI.

Acids.		A/5 Serum.	A Serum.
Nitric	N/200	2.3 c.c.	6.8 c.c.
Hydrochloric	N/200	2.4	7.0
Sulphuric	N/200	2.5	7.2
Phosphoric	N/50	2.0	4.7
Formic	N/50	0.50	1.85
Acetic	N/50	0.50	1.9
Monochloroacetic	N/50	0.60	1.8
Dichloroacetic	N/50	0.60	2.0
Trichloroacetic	N/50	0.65	2.0
Oxalic	N/100	0.70	3.2
Tartaric	N/100	0.85	4.0
Citric	N/100	0.85	2.8

The above Tables IX, X and XI show that serum becomes more stable towards dilution when coagulated by salts of monovalent cations as sodium acetate, potassium fluoride, etc., whilst it behaves normally towards dilution when coagulated by either polyvalent cations or acids.

In the following tables the results are recorded when serum is coagulated by pairs of electrolytes.

2 C.c. of diluted (five times) serum taken.

Total volume ... 10 c.c.

Time of observation ... 1 hour.

TABLE XII.

Electrolytes added in c.c.		Amount of copper sulphate N/200 to coagulate in c.c.
—		0.20
0.2 c.c. of N/10 KOH	...	4.50
0.2 c.c. of 0.14M sodium citrate	...	1.90
0.1 c.c. of 1.78M sodium tartrate	...	4.00
0.20 c.c. of 3.46M sodium acetate	...	0.90

TABLE XIII.

Electrolytes added in c.c.	Amount of ferric chloride N/95.7 to coagulate in c.c.
—	0.20
0.2 c.c. of N/10 KOH	2.8
0.2 c.c. of 0.14M sodium citrate	6.3
0.2 c.c. of 0.178M sodium tartrate	2.5
0.2 c.c. of 3.46M sodium acetate	3.0

Thus, marked stabilisation has been observed when serum is coagulated by copper sulphate or ferric chloride in presence of very small quantities of potassium hydroxide, sodium acetate, tartrate, or citrate.

Coagulation by pairs of electrolytes.

2 C.c. of original serum taken.

Total volume ... 10 c.c.

Time of observation ... 1 hour.

TABLE XIV.

Sodium chloride + Cerous nitrate.

Amount of NaCl 0.1076N added in c.c.	Amount of cerous nitrate N/100 to coagulate in c.c.
0	4.10
8	0
0.2	4.40
0.50	4.70
1.0	4.85

TABLE XV.

Sodium chloride + Hydrochloric acid.

Amount of NaCl 0.1076N added in c.c.	Amount of HCl N/100 to coagulate in c.c.
0	3.6
8	0
0.2	3.95
0.5	4.30
1.0	5.25

TABLE XVI.

Barium chloride + Hydrochloric acid.

Amount of BaCl ₂ 0.0855N added in c.c.	Amount of HCl N/100 to coagulate in c.c.
0	3.7
8	0
0.2	4.0
0.5	4.5
1.0	5.2

TABLE XVII.

Cerous nitrate + Hydrochloric acid.

Amount of HCl N/100 added in c.c.	N/100 cerous nitrate to coagulate in c.c.			% Difference.
	Observed.	Calculated.	Difference.	
0	3.05	—	—	—
3.7	0	—	—	—
0.2	2.9	2.85	+0.01	+0.03
0.5	2.75	2.65	0.1	+3.6
1.0	2.05	2.13	-0.08	-4

TABLE XVIII.

Potassium oxalate + Hydrochloric acid.

Amount of HCl N/100 added in c.c.	1.5M potassium oxalate to coagulate in c.c.			% Difference.
	Observed.	Calculated.	Difference.	
0	6.0	—	—	—
3.7	0	—	—	—
0.2	6.0	5.67	+0.33	+5.5
0.5	6.1	5.12	+0.98	+14.4
1.0	6.2	4.38	+1.82	+29.0

TABLE XIX.

Potassium fluoride + Hydrochloric acid.

Amount of HCl N/100 added in c.c.	8.0 N K_2F_2 to coagulate in c.c.			% Difference
	Observed.	Calculated.	Difference.	
0	1.9	—	—	—
3.7	0	—	—	—
0.2	1.95	1.8	+0.15	+7.7
0.5	1.90	1.75	+0.15	+7.9
1.0	1.9	1.59	+0.31	+16.0

TABLE XX.

Sodium chloride + Oxalic acid.

Amount of NaCl 0.1076N added in c.c.	Amount of oxalic acid N/100 to coagulate in c.c.
0	... 4.1
0.2	... 4.4
0.5	... 4.7
1.0	... 4.85

TABLE XXI.

Potassium fluoride + Dichloroacetic acid.

Amount of dichloroacetic acid N/50 added in c.c.	Amount of 8'0N K_2F_6 to coagulate in c.c.			%
	Observed.	Calculated.	Difference.	Difference.
0	1.9	—	—	—
2.0	0	—	—	—
0.2	1.9	1.71	+0.19	+10
0.5	1.9	1.43	+0.47	+25
1.0	1.9	0.95	+0.95	+50

TABLE XXII.

Trichloroacetic acid + Sodium acetate.

Amount of trichloroacetic acid N/50 added in c.c.	Amount of sodium acetate 4'07M to coagulate in c.c.			%
	Observed.	Calculated.	Difference.	Difference.
0	6.6	—	—	—
2.0	0	—	—	—
0.2	6.5	5.94	+0.56	+9.5
0.5	6.65	4.95	+1.70	+34.3
1.0	6.70	3.3	+3.4	+103.0

From Tables XIV to XXII, it is seen that antagonistic effect is observed when serum is coagulated with mixtures of sodium chloride + cerous nitrate, sodium chloride + HCl, $BaCl_2$ + HCl, $K_2C_2O_4$ + HCl, K_2F_6 + HCl, $NaCl$ + $H_2C_2O_4$, K_2F_6 + dichloroacetic acid, and trichloroacetic acid + sodium acetate. When however, the serum is coagulated with mixtures of cerous nitrate and hydrochloric acid, additive amounts of these electrolytes precipitate the sol.

The phenomenon of acclimatisation has been studied with different acids and salts at different dilutions of the serum. In the following table, the results with acids and salts of polyvalent cations with a concentrated serum are recorded.

TABLE XXIII.

Original serum taken	... 2 c.c.
Total volume	... 10 c.c.
Time of acclimatisation experiments	... 6 hours.
Time of observation	... 1 hour after adding the last quantity of electrolyte.

Electrolytes.	Amount to coagulate when added all at once.	Quantity added at a time for slow addition.	Amount to coagulate when slowly added.	% Increment.
Nitric N/200	... 6.8 c.c.	1 c.c.	8.5 c.c.	25
Hydrochloric N/200	... 7.0	1	9.0	28.5
Sulphuric N/200	... 7.2	1	9.4	30.5
Phosphoric N/50	... 4.7	0.8	6.4	29.8
Formic N/50	... 1.85	0.2	2.55	38.8
Acetic N/50	... 1.9	0.25	3.0	57.8
Monochloroacetic N/50	... 1.8	0.3	2.70	50.0
Dichloroacetic N/50	... 2.0	0.3	2.45	22.0
Trichloroacetic N/50	... 2.0	0.3	2.4	20.0
Oxalic N/100	... 3.2	0.4	4.9	53.1
Tartaric N/100	... 4.0	0.5	6.3	57.5
Citric N/100	... 2.8	0.2	3.7	32.1
Aluminium nitrate N/200	5.2	0.7	9.7	86.5
Cerous nitrate N/200	... 5.35	0.7	8.9	66.3
Thorium nitrate N/200	... 5.6	0.7	8.4	50.0

We shall now give our results with diluted serum where the phenomenon of acclimatization is studied with acids and salts of polyvalent cations.

TABLE XXIV.

2 C. c. of diluted (five times) serum taken.

Electrolytes.	Amount to coagulate when added all at once.	Quantity added at a time for slow addition.	Amount to coagulate when slowly added.	% Increment
Nitric N/200	2.3 c. c.	0.3 c. c.	2.6 c. c.	13
Hydrochloric N/200	2.4	0.8	2.7	12.5
Phosphoric N/50	2.0	0.3	2.35	17.5
Formic N/50	0.5	0.05	0.85	30.0
Acetic N/50	0.5	0.05	0.65	30.0
Monochloroacetic N/50	0.6	0.05	0.75	25.0
Dichloroacetic N/50	0.6	0.05	0.70	16.6
Trichloroacetic N/50	0.65	0.05	0.75	15.4
Oxalic N/100	0.75	0.1	1.05	40.0
Tartaric N/100	0.85	0.1	1.10	29.0
Citric N/100	0.85	0.1	0.95	11.8
Aluminium nitrate N/200	1.5	0.2	2.2	46.6
Cerous nitrate N/200	1.65	0.2	2.3	39.4
Thorium nitrate N/200	1.7	0.2	1.8	5.9

The results on acclimatization in presence of salts of univalent cations with concentrated and dilute serums are given below :

2 C.c. of original serum taken.

Serum A/2—when 1 c.c. of original serum used in experiments with dilute serum.

Time of observation—1 hour after adding the last quantity of electrolyte.

Time of acclimatization experiments—7 hours.

Total volume—10 c.c. when all electrolyte was added at once.

TABLE XXV.

With Serum A.

Electrolytes.	Amount to coagulate when added all at once.	Quantity added at a time for slow addition.	Amount to coagulate when slowly added.	% Increment.
Sodium acetate 4.07 M	6.6 c. c.	1.0 c. c.	17 c. c.	175
Sodium tartrate 1.32 M	6.9	1.0	11.3	63.7
Potassium flouride 8 N	1.9	0.2	1.9	0
Potassium oxalate 1.5 M	6.45	0.8	6.4	-0.8

TABLE XXVI.

With Serum A/2.

Electrolytes.	Amount to coagulate when added all at once.	Quantity added at a time for slow addition.	Amount to coagulate when slowly added.	% Increment.
Sodium acetate 4.07 M	7.4 c. c.	1.5 c. c.	19.5 c. c.	...
Sodium tartrate 1.32 M	7.5	1.0	13.2	76
Potassium fluoride 8N	2.1	0.2	2.1	0
Potassium oxalate 1.5M	6.8	0.8	6.95	2.2

It will be seen that the percentage of positive acclimatization is more pronounced with a concentrated serum than a dilute one, when the coagulation is effected by acids and salts like aluminium nitrate, thorium nitrate, and cerous nitrate. On the other hand, this phenomenon is developed more with dilute serum than concentrated one with electrolytes like sodium acetate and sodium tartrate. The phenomenon is, however, not at all developed with either potassium fluoride, or potassium oxalate. This seems to be due to the formation of insoluble calcium salts from the presence of calcium ions in sheep serum. The foregoing results are comparative as the serums used had the same p_H value.

We have shown in a previous paper that the relative checking of hydrolysis is greater when small amounts of an acid are used than when large amounts are added. Consequently, when small quantities of an acid are added to a hydrolysable sol, it will be rendered relatively more unstable and it coagulates more readily on further addition of an acid than when it is added all at once.

We have already shown that when arsenious and antimony sulphides, Prussian blue, cupric ferrocyanide, mastic, gamboge and gum dammar are coagulated by mixtures of an acid and a salt, the amount of salt necessary to complete the coagulation is much less than the additive amounts. It is clear, therefore, that with these sols the influence of the checking of hydrolysis in presence of acids is more important and more than counterbalances the effect of adsorption of similarly charged ions.

On the other hand, our experimental results show marked ionic antagonism when sheep serum is coagulated by mixtures of acid and salt and marked positive acclimatization is observed even when the serum is coagulated by acids. It is evident, therefore, that in the case of serum, the influence of similarly charged ions is more

important than the checking of the hydrolysis by acids. When, however, very diluted serums are used the hydrolysis of serum is increased and in these cases the amount of positive acclimatization is appreciably less than in the case of concentrated serum. The cases of negative acclimatization already observed by us in previous papers were due to the high adsorption of the oppositely charged ion in comparison with the adsorption of the similarly charged ion. The cases of negative acclimatization as observed in this paper are caused mainly by the redering of the sols unstable due to checking of hydrolysis by acids.

In a previous paper (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1927, 31, 187) we have shown that the sols of Prussian blue, mastic, gum dammar and gamboge require much larger quantities of a mono-valent salt in the diluted condition than the concentrated. The ionic antagonism, however, is not so highly developed with these sols. We are of the opinion that on dilution these hydrolysable sols become stable due to two causes: (1) The increase in the degree of hydrolysis and (2) the increase in the ratio of the adsorption of the negative to that of the positive ion. We have already quantitatively shown that the above sols are more hydrolysed than sols of either arsenious or antimony sulphides.

In the case of ionic antagonism when the sols are coagulated by mixtures of electrolytes, in the decrease of viscosity of sols on the addition of small amounts of electrolytes and in the phenomenon of positive acclimatization the influence of similarly charged ions is the dominant factor.

It has been shown in this laboratory that blood behaves as a sol capable of adsorbing similarly charged ions. Our experimental results on the coagulation of serum indicate that serum is also capable of adsorbing similarly charged ions and hence dilute serum is more stable towards electrolytes than concentrated serum. The phenomena of ionic antagonism and positive acclimatization are also evident in this colloid. Serum, however, appears not to be hydrolysed to the same extent as the gums, Prussian blue, copper ferrocyanide and arsenious sulphide and possibly does not adsorb the coagulating ion very highly and consequently the phenomenon of negative acclimatization is not observed in the coagulation of serum by different acids. In this case the capacity of adsorbing similarly charged ions is highly developed and in all cases we observe the phenomenon of positive acclimatization and ionic antagonism.

Freundlich's ("Kappillar-Chemie", 1922, p. 628) explanation of positive acclimatisation based on the difference in the rates of diffusion of the added electrolytes when the addition is rapid and slow is untenable because the mixtures are always stirred and thoroughly mixed.

Weiser (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1926, 30, 20) has tried to explain the phenomenon of acclimatisation from the view-point of the adsorption of electrolytes by the coagulated mass. From our experiments on the adsorption of electrolytes by precipitated substances, we find that ferric hydroxide is a better adsorbent than arsenious sulphide. Moreover, partial coagulation takes place with both the sols of ferric hydroxide and arsenious sulphide. Hence Weiser's view cannot explain the occurrence of the phenomenon more markedly with arsenious sulphide sol than with ferric hydroxide sol when coagulated by KCl, K_2SO_4 , and $BaCl_2$.

According to Bancroft ("Applied Colloid Chemistry", 1921, p. 220) the first addition of an electrolyte causes a slight agglomeration, which is not sufficient to cause precipitation, but which cuts down the adsorbing power of the colloid, so that more salt is necessary to cause the same amount of adsorption. Now if the explanation of Bancroft be correct, the adsorption of barium ions by a sol of arsenious sulphide should be less when the addition is slow than when it is rapid, provided the same amount of the electrolyte is added in both the cases. We have, however, shown from adsorption experiments on the coagulation of arsenious sulphide that the adsorption of barium ions is much greater when the addition is slow than when it is rapid. Hence Bancroft's explanation is unsound.

We have already explained the phenomenon of positive acclimatisation from the point of view of the adsorption of similarly charged ions. When drops of barium chloride are added to a sol of arsenious sulphide, the sol is appreciably stabilised by the adsorption of chloride ions and hence greater quantities of barium chloride are necessary to coagulate the sol completely. From our experiments we have shown that the adsorption of barium ions is greater when the addition is slow than when it is rapid, simply because when small quantities of barium chloride are added to arsenious sulphide, the charge on the particle of the sol is increased by adsorption of chloride ions and hence greater amount of adsorption of barium ions is necessary to coagulate the sol.

We were the first to observe the phenomenon of negative acclimatisation and to offer an explanation of this interesting phenomenon, which is inexplicable from the views of Weiser and Bancroft. We have carried on quantitative experiments on the adsorption of silver and cupric ions in the slow and rapid coagulations of manganese dioxide sol by silver nitrate and cupric sulphate, and in these cases the phenomenon of negative acclimatisation has been observed.

25 C.c. of manganese dioxide containing 1 gm. MnO_2 per litre were rapidly mixed and coagulated with 14 c.c. N/100 $AgNO_3$ when 1.28 millimoles of Ag were adsorbed by the sol. On the other hand, 1.25 millimoles of Ag were adsorbed by the same amount of manganese dioxide when 13 c.c. of N/100 $AgNO_3$ were added slowly, 1 c.c. of the solution being added to the sol at a time. With $CuSO_4$ the adsorption of Cu ions was very high, the whole amount of the added copper salt was adsorbed by manganese dioxide sol at the precipitating concentration of $CuSO_4$ when the electrolyte is added either slowly or rapidly.

Our results with $AgNO_3$ prove that the percentage of adsorption of Ag is 91 when the addition of the electrolyte is rapid and it is 96 when the addition is slow, proving that when the addition is slow slightly smaller quantities of the electrolyte would be sufficient to coagulate the sol and the phenomenon of negative acclimatization would develop. We have also observed that in the coagulation of arsenious sulphide and antimony sulphide by crystal violet, methylene blue, etc. the phenomenon of negative acclimatization is developed and these coagulating agents are completely adsorbed by the sol at the precipitating concentrations. These results are also interesting from the point of view that the phenomenon of negative acclimatization will be observed only in those cases where the adsorption of the oppositely charged ion is very prominent and the adsorption of the ion carrying the same charge is practically negligible.

Summary.

1. The phenomenon of acclimatization has been studied with concentrated and diluted sols of arsenious sulphide, mastic and gamboge. In all cases negative acclimatization has been observed when the sols are coagulated by acids. This is more marked with a dilute sol than a concentrated one.

2. Polyvalent cations and acids possess high coagulating powers towards sheep serum. The stability of a diluted serum towards its coagulation by univalent ions from salts like sodium acetate, potassium fluoride, potassium oxalate, etc., is far greater than a concentrated serum. On the other hand, smaller amounts of acids and polyvalent cations coagulate a dilute serum than a concentrated one.

3. Ionic antagonism is developed when serum is coagulated by mixtures of cations of varying valencies or an acid and a salt.

4. The phenomenon of positive acclimatization is observed when serum is coagulated by either acids or salts and it is more marked with salts than with acids. With potassium fluoride and potassium oxalate, no positive acclimatization is observed because of the formation of calcium fluoride and oxalate from the calcium ions present in serum. The phenomenon of acclimatization is more marked for the dilute serum than the concentrated one when coagulated by salts. With acids the phenomenon is less developed with dilute serum.

5. Sheep serum, therefore, behaves in certain respects, like sols of mastic, gamboge, arsenious sulphide, etc. and is capable of adsorbing similarly charged ions from coagulating electrolytes. It is however not hydrolysed to the same extent as the gums, Prussian blue, and cupric ferrocyanide and possibly does not adsorb the coagulating ion very highly.

6. The phenomenon of negative acclimatization observed in the coagulation of the highly hydrolysable sols (gum dammar, gamboge, mastic, etc.) by acids originates from the checking of hydrolysis of the sols by acids.

7. Ionic antagonism, decrease of viscosity of sols in presence of small amounts of electrolytes and positive acclimatization are due mainly to the adsorption of similarly charged ions. The abnormal dilution effect of hydrolysable sols is due to two causes: (1) Increase in the degree of hydrolysis of the sols on dilution and (2) the increase in the ratio of the adsorption of the negative to that of the positive ion on dilution.

8. The phenomenon of negative acclimatization first observed in this laboratory cannot be explained from the view-points of Freundlich, Bancroft and Weiser and depends on the high adsorbability of the coagulating ion by the sol. This phenomenon will only be observed in those cases where the adsorption of the oppositely charged ions is very high and that of the similarly charged ions is negligible.